

DEGRADATION MODELS OF CRITICAL COMPONENTS TO ASSESS THEIR LIFETIME

Project Information	
Acronym - Title	ICONIC – Smart, Aware, Integrated Wind Farm Control Interacting with Digital Twins
Project no.	101122329
Call // Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03 // HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-03-04
Type of action // Service	HORIZON-RIA // CINEA/C/02
Project duration // starting and end date	48 months // 1/12/2023 – 30/11/2027
Website	www.iconicwind.org
Deliverable Information	
Number & Title	D30/D4.3 - Degradation models of critical components to assess their lifetime
WP number and title	WP4 - Digital twins of wind farms and wind turbines with critical components to improve control
Author	David Cubillas, Mario Alvarez (IKERLAN), Igor Reinares (LAULAGUN), Arkaitz Lopez (BEARINN), Matteo Kirchner, Ilian Sterckx (KU Leuven), Jelle Bosmans (ZF Wind Power), Mostafa Valavi, Maria Rostad (EDRMedeso), Cees Taal, and Stephan Baggerohr (SKF).
Description	Degradation models of critical components to assess their lifetime. It corresponds to T4.3: Degradation models to assess lifetime of critical components.
Lead Beneficiary	IKL, IKERLAN
Type	R: Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU: Public
Status	Final
History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Draft created by IKL (17/02/2026)
Version 0.2	Draft approved by WP4 (14/05/2026)
Version 1	Draft approved by TC and General Assembly (29.05.2026)

Copyright

This work is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

TABLE OF CONTENT

Abbreviations and acronyms	3
1 Executive Summary.....	4
2 Introduction.....	5
2.1 Link to other project WPs and deliverables	5
3 Degradation model of the gearbox.....	7
3.1 Introduction to the gearbox degradation model	7
3.2 Degradation model of the gearbox	7
3.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities	17
4 Degradation model of the generator	18
4.1 Introduction to the generator degradation model	18
4.2 Degradation model of the generator	19
4.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities	23
5 Degradation model of the main bearing	24
5.1 Introduction to the main bearing degradation model.....	24
5.2 Degradation model of the main bearing.....	25
5.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities	28
6 Degradation model of the pitch and yaw bearing	29
6.1 Introduction to the pitch and yaw bearing degradation models.....	29
6.2 Degradation model of the pitch and yaw bearing	30
6.3 Degradation modelling under variable loading for online predictions.....	39
6.4 Conclusions and links to the other project activities	46
7 Conclusions	48
8 References	49

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Damage
DoA	Description of Action
DT	Digital Twin
FEM	Finite Element Method
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
GA	General Assembly
HFM	High-Fidelity Model
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCoE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
MFM	Mid-Fidelity Model
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PM	Permanent Magnet
RCF	Rolling Contact Fatigue
ROM	Reduced Order Model
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
S–N	Stress–Number of cycles fatigue curve
TFF	Tooth Flank Fracture
USL	Updated Statistical Life
WP	Work Package
WT	Wind Turbine

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the degradation models developed in Task 4.3 of the ICONIC project to assess lifetime consumption of critical wind turbine components. The work provides the degradation modelling layer within WP4, enabling local physical responses obtained from component models to be translated into damage indicators, lifetime consumption metrics and component-level degradation descriptors.

The work builds directly on Task 4.2, where high-fidelity component models were developed to estimate the local response of wind turbine critical components under external wind and control loads. These local responses include winding temperatures in the generator, contact loads and pressures in bearings, subsurface stress fields, and gear contact conditions. In D4.3, these quantities are used as inputs to component-specific degradation models formulated according to the dominant failure mechanisms affecting each component family.

The deliverable covers the critical drivetrain and orientation-system components identified in the project: generator, main bearing, pitch bearings, yaw bearing, and gearbox. For the generator, the degradation model focuses on thermal ageing of the winding insulation under variable thermal loading. For the main bearing, bearing life assessment methods are applied using realistic load distributions obtained from sensor-based measurements. For the pitch and yaw bearings, Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF) is addressed through the evaluation of multiaxial subsurface fatigue parameters and damage accumulation strategies under variable loading conditions. For the gearbox, the degradation modelling work addresses the gear failure mechanisms considered in this deliverable, including contact fatigue, bending-related cracking, tooth flank fracture and micropitting-related phenomena.

A specific contribution of D4.3 is the definition of degradation modelling approaches that can support future digital twin implementation. The models are discussed in terms of their physical relevance, required input quantities, output indicators, compatibility with variable operational loads, and potential for reduction or reformulation into fast prediction models. Where applicable, standard-based engineering approaches are used, while additional formulations are introduced to support damage tracking and lifetime assessment under variable operating conditions.

At this stage, the models presented in this deliverable should be understood as the analytical and methodological foundation for component lifetime assessment within the ICONIC turbine-level digital twin framework. Their reduction, integration and formal validation under representative operational and experimental conditions will be addressed in subsequent project activities. In this context, D4.3 establishes the basis for future use of degradation indicators in predictive maintenance, lifetime-aware control and LCOE-oriented decision-making within the ICONIC framework.

2 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the degradation modelling activities carried out in Task 4.3 of the ICONIC project. The purpose of this task is to develop component-specific models capable of assessing degradation and lifetime consumption of critical wind turbine components under realistic operating conditions. These models represent an intermediate layer between the physical response predicted by component models and the future use of degradation indicators within digital twin and control-oriented frameworks.

The work focuses on components that are relevant for wind turbine reliability, operation and maintenance costs, and control-induced fatigue. These include drivetrain components, such as the generator, main bearing and gearbox, as well as orientation-system components, namely pitch and yaw bearings. For each component family, the degradation model is defined according to the dominant physical failure mechanisms, the available input quantities, and the type of degradation indicator required for subsequent integration in the ICONIC digital twin framework.

The deliverable is organised into component-specific sections: The gearbox section (section 3) addresses gear degradation mechanisms relevant to the available operational and test-rig information, including contact fatigue, bending-related cracking, tooth flank fracture and micropitting-related phenomena. The generator section (section 4) addresses insulation ageing driven by thermal loading. The main bearing (section 5) section focuses on bearing lifetime assessment using measured load distributions and standardised bearing life calculation methods. The pitch and yaw bearing section (section 5) develops a Rolling Contact Fatigue framework for large slewing bearings operating under variable loads, including both reference cycle-counting approaches and incremental damage formulations.

2.1 Link to other project WPs and deliverables

The results presented in this deliverable are closely linked to several ICONIC work packages and deliverables.

Within WP4, D4.3 builds directly on D4.2, where high-fidelity and component-level models of the wind turbine and its critical components were developed. These models provide the physical quantities required by the degradation models, including thermal fields, contact pressures, subsurface stresses, bearing loads and gear contact conditions. Therefore, D4.2 provides the physics-based response layer, while D4.3 provides the degradation and lifetime assessment layer.

The outputs of D4.3 will support D4.4, where component models and degradation models will be reduced or reformulated into fast prediction models suitable for integration into the ICONIC digital twin framework. In that context, the degradation indicators developed in this deliverable will provide the basis for tracking component lifetime consumption and for supporting future health and lifetime assessment functionalities.

D4.3 is also connected to D4.5, where the digital twin developments will be considered within the wind farm control framework. The degradation indicators developed here may contribute to the evaluation of the impact of control strategies on component lifetime, supporting lifetime-aware control, risk-level assessment and LCOE-oriented decision-making.

The deliverable is also linked to WP2 and WP3. The wind farm and turbine control strategies developed in these work packages define operating conditions and control actions that influence component loading and fatigue. Conversely, the degradation indicators developed in D4.3 can provide relevant information for assessing how different control strategies affect component lifetime consumption.

Finally, D4.3 is closely connected to WP5. Previous validation activities, such as those reported in D5.4, provide relevant context regarding the accuracy of component models used as input to degradation assessment. Further validation of lifetime prediction and degradation indicators will be addressed in subsequent WP5 activities, particularly D5.5, using dedicated and/or historical operational and test-rig data. These activities will be essential to assess the applicability of the degradation models before their use in integrated digital twin and control demonstrations.

3 DEGRADATION MODEL OF THE GEARBOX

3.1 Introduction to the gearbox degradation model

The degradation models for the wind turbine gearbox presented in this work consider the four dominant failure mechanisms: pitting, tooth bending, tooth flank fracture and micropitting. These failure modes are defined and described in the ISO 6336 standard [1].

For pitting and tooth bending, the standard provides detailed methodologies that allow cumulative damage to be calculated incrementally for each load iteration. In contrast, tooth flank fracture and micropitting are evaluated using safety factor calculations rather than cumulative damage approaches.

A comparison is performed between two different calculation approaches. The first method uses a 10-minute averaged torque signal, which represents the current state-of-the-art industry practice. The second method employs a higher-resolution approach, using torque measurements at one-second intervals. The results show an average difference of approximately 10% between the two methods. This discrepancy arises because the 10-minute average smooths out torque peaks, which significantly influence damage accumulation due to the exponential nature of S–N curves.

In the last part, special attention is given to the mesh load factor in the planetary stages. The ISO 6336 standard prescribes a conservative value for this factor, which can lead to an overestimation of the damage. To address this limitation, a similar method to the one proposed by UNAI [2] is applied to historical measurement data obtained from a ZF test rig. This method enables a more accurate estimation of the mesh load factor, which can then be incorporated into the damage calculations.

The accuracy of these degradation models will be validated by comparing the predicted results with observed gearbox failures in operational data. This validation study will be reported in Deliverable D5.5.

3.2 Degradation model of the gearbox

This section presents the modelling approaches for the four dominant gear failure modes: pitting, tooth bending, tooth flank fracture, and micropitting. It also includes a comparison of different damage calculation methods. Finally, a strain-based measurement on the ring gear is used to estimate the mesh load factor for each planet, which will subsequently be incorporated into the degradation models.

The starting point for these calculations is the determination of the tangential force on the gear F_t . This is calculated as follows [1]:

$$F_t = \frac{2000 \cdot T}{d} \cdot K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_{H\beta(F\beta)} \cdot K_{H\alpha(F\alpha)} \cdot K_Y$$

where:

F_t : tangential load (N)

T : torque (Nm)

d : pitch diameter (mm)

K_A : application factor, accounts for external load variations (e.g. wind turbulence, start/stop)

K_V : dynamic factor, accounts for internal dynamic effects (vibrations, gear inaccuracies)

$K_{H\beta(F\beta)}$: transverse load factor, accounts for uneven load sharing along the line of action for contact stress (for root stress)

$K_{H\alpha(F\alpha)}$: face load factor, accounts for load distribution across the face width for contact stress (for root stress)

K_V : mesh load factor, accounts for the difference in load between planets, only applicable in the planetary stages, and will be discussed in more detail later.

3.2.1 Pitting failure mode

Pitting is a surface fatigue phenomenon that occurs on the gear tooth flanks due to repeated rolling–sliding contact between meshing teeth. Small cracks initiate below the surface under cyclic contact stress and propagate toward the surface, eventually leading to the formation of small pits (see Figure 1). Over time, this damage can grow and significantly affect gear performance [3].

The severity of pitting depends on its progression. Initial pitting may be acceptable, as it can stabilize after a running-in phase and even improve load distribution. However, a continuous increase in the number or size of pits is considered unacceptable, as it reduces the effective contact area and may ultimately lead to failure.

Figure 1: Surface fatigue damage in the form of pitting on the gear tooth flank [4]

According to ISO 6336, pitting is evaluated based on the contact stress acting on the tooth flanks. The contact stress is calculated as:

$$\sigma_H = Z_H \cdot Z_E \cdot Z_\varepsilon \cdot Z_\beta \cdot \sqrt{\frac{F_t}{b \cdot d_1} \cdot \frac{u + 1}{u}}$$

where:

- σ_H : contact stress (MPa)
- Z_H : zone factor (accounts for Hertzian contact conditions)
- Z_E : elasticity factor (depends on material properties)
- Z_ε : contact ratio factor
- Z_β : helix angle factor
- F_t : tangential force at the pitch circle (N)
- b : face width (mm)
- d_1 : reference diameter of the pinion (mm)
- u : gear ratio ($u = z_2/z_1$)

The calculated contact stress is compared with the allowable contact stress to assess the load level.

The allowable stress is:

$$\sigma_{H,lim} = \sigma_{H,lim}^0 \cdot Z_{NT} \cdot Z_L \cdot Z_V \cdot Z_R \cdot Z_W \cdot Z_X \cdot Z_Z$$

where:

- $\sigma_{H,lim}^0$: reference fatigue limit (material)
- Z_{NT} : life factor
- Z_L : lubrication factor
- Z_V : velocity factor
- Z_R : roughness factor
- Z_W : work hardening factor
- Z_X : size factor
- Z_Z : reliability factor

For varying loads, pitting damage is accumulated using the Palmgren–Miner rule. The number of cycles to failure is obtained from the S–N curve:

$$N_i = \left(\frac{\sigma_{H,lim}}{\sigma_{H,i}} \right)^m$$

The accumulated damage is then:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i}$$

with n_i the number of cycles for load level i . Failure due to pitting is expected when $D = 1$.

3.2.2 Tooth bending failure mode

Tooth bending failure occurs at the root of the gear tooth, where tensile stresses are highest during operation. Under repeated loading, cracks initiate at the tooth root and propagate until the tooth fractures (see Figure 2). Such failure is critical, as the breakage of a single tooth can lead to severe damage or even complete failure of the transmission. For this reason, ISO 6336-3 recommends that the safety factor against tooth bending failure is chosen higher than that for pitting, ensuring a sufficiently low probability of catastrophic failure [5].

Figure 2: Tooth failure due to bending fatigue at the root of the gear tooth [6]

ISO 6336-3 evaluates tooth bending based on the tooth root stress, calculated as [5]:

$$\sigma_F = \frac{F_t}{b \cdot m_n} \cdot Y_F \cdot Y_S \cdot Y_\beta \cdot Y_B \cdot Y_{DT} \cdot Y_Z$$

where:

- σ_F : tooth root bending stress (MPa)

- F_t : tangential force (N)
- b : face width (mm)
- m_n : normal module (mm)
- Y_F : tooth form factor
- Y_S : stress correction factor (accounts for stress concentration)
- Y_β : helix angle factor
- Y_B : rim thickness factor
- Y_{DT} : deep tooth factor
- Y_Z : reliability factor

The calculated bending stress is compared with the allowable bending stress.

$$\sigma_{F,lim} = \sigma_{F,lim}^0 \cdot Y_{NT} \cdot Y_\delta \cdot Y_R \cdot Y_X$$

where:

- $\sigma_{F,lim}^0$: reference bending fatigue limit
- Y_{NT} : life factor
- Y_δ : notch sensitivity factor
- Y_R : surface roughness factor
- Y_X : size factor

Similar to pitting: for variable loading conditions, fatigue damage is accumulated using the Palmgren–Miner rule. The S–N relation for bending is:

$$N_i = \left(\frac{\sigma_{F,lim}}{\sigma_{F,i}} \right)^m$$

and the cumulative damage is:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i}$$

with n_i the number of cycles for load level i . Failure is expected when the accumulated damage $D = 1$

3.2.3 Tooth flank fracture failure mode

Tooth flank fracture is a subsurface fatigue failure that originates below the active contact area of a gear tooth (see Figure 3). Unlike pitting or bending, the damage is not initiated at the surface or the tooth root, but develops within the material due to cyclic shear stresses caused by the contact between meshing gears. [7]

Figure 3: Subsurface-initiated tooth flank fracture, where a crack originating below the contact surface propagates through the material and results in sudden tooth breakage. [6]

The crack typically starts at a certain depth below the surface, often around the case–core interface in case-hardened gears. From there, it propagates both toward the surface and deeper into the material. Since the material near the surface is harder, crack growth is usually faster toward the core. Once the crack reaches the surface, rapid propagation occurs and leads to sudden tooth fracture. In many cases, this failure occurs without visible surface damage beforehand, which makes it difficult to detect in operation.

This failure mode is particularly relevant for wind turbine gearboxes [8], including the C-Power turbines, where it is frequently observed even when gears fulfil standard pitting and bending criteria. This highlights that tooth flank fracture is governed by different mechanisms than the more classical failure modes.

The ISO 6336-4 method evaluates tooth flank fracture by comparing the local stress state inside the material with the local material strength, rather than using a surface-based stress comparison [7].

The key idea is to evaluate, at different positions on the tooth flank and at different depths in the material:

- The equivalent shear stress, $\tau_{eff}(y)$
- The material shear strength, $\tau_{per}(y)$

These are combined into the local material exposure [7]:

$$A_{FF}(y) = \frac{\tau_{eff}(y)}{\tau_{per}(y)} + c_1$$

where:

$A_{FF}(y)$: local material exposure

c_1 : calibration factor (≈ 0.04 for case carburized steels)

Only depths larger than roughly half the contact width are considered, since this corresponds to the location of maximum subsurface shear stress.

The contact conditions are determined from the Hertzian contact theory. The characteristic contact width is given by [7]:

$$b_H = 4 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{p_{dyn} \cdot \rho_{red}}{E_r}}$$

where:

b_H : half contact width

p_{dyn} : local contact stress

ρ_{red} : relative curvature

E_r : reduced elastic modulus

For all considered contact points and depths, the maximum material exposure is determined:

$$A_{FF,max} = \max(A_{FF}(y))$$

Experimental observations show that values of $A_{FF,max} = 0.8$ can already lead to tooth flank fracture under constant loading.

It is important to note that this method does not include cumulative fatigue damage, unlike pitting and bending. Instead, it provides a local, instantaneous assessment of the material state. This is particularly relevant for applications with highly variable loads, such as wind turbines, where the highest load peaks play a dominant role in driving the failure behaviour.

3.2.4 Micropitting failure mode

Micropitting is a surface fatigue phenomenon that occurs in rolling–sliding contact under mixed or boundary lubrication conditions (see Figure 4). It is characterized by the formation of many small surface cracks that grow into shallow pits, typically on the order of 10–20 μm deep. [8]

Figure 4: Micropitting damage on the gear tooth flank, characterized by numerous small surface pits [9]

The occurrence of micropitting is strongly influenced by operating conditions, including load, sliding velocity, temperature, surface roughness, and lubricant properties. It is most critical in regions with negative sliding and is commonly observed in hardened gear materials.

Micropitting can stabilize after an initial running-in phase. However, if it continues to develop, it may lead to increased noise, higher dynamic loads, and eventually evolve into more severe failure modes such as macropitting.

The ISO 6336 method evaluates micropitting based on the lubrication conditions in the contact zone, rather than purely on stress levels. The key parameter is the specific lubricant film thickness, which compares the oil film thickness to the surface roughness.

The local specific film thickness is defined as:

$$\lambda_{GF,y} = \frac{h_Y}{R_a}$$

where:

$\lambda_{GF,y}$: local specific film thickness

h_Y : local lubricant film thickness (μm)

R_a : effective surface roughness

The effective roughness is given by:

$$R_a = 0.5 \cdot (R_{a1} + R_{a2})$$

with:

R_{a1}, R_{a2} : roughness of pinion and wheel

The local lubricant film thickness is calculated using:

$$h_Y = 1600 \cdot \rho_{n,Y}^{0.6} \cdot G_M^{0.7} \cdot U_Y^{0.7} \cdot W_Y^{-0.13} \cdot S_{GF,Y}^{0.22}$$

where:

$\rho_{n,Y}$: local radius of curvature

G_M : material parameter

U_Y : velocity parameter

W_Y : load parameter

$S_{GF,Y}$: sliding parameter

From all evaluated contact points, the minimum value is taken:

$$\lambda_{GF,min} = \min(\lambda_{GF,y})$$

The resistance against micropitting is expressed through a safety factor:

$$S_\lambda = \frac{\lambda_{GF,min}}{\lambda_{GFP}}$$

where:

λ_{GFP} : permissible specific film thickness

The permissible film thickness λ_{GFP} is typically determined from experimental data or service experience, as it strongly depends on lubricant properties and operating conditions.

In practice, some degree of micropitting may be acceptable if it stabilizes over time. However, for critical applications or strict performance requirements, a higher safety factor is required to prevent its occurrence.

3.2.5 Damage calculation methods

This section evaluates how load representation influences the calculated fatigue damage in the gearbox. Figure 5 compares damage calculations performed using one month of operational data for the parallel helical gears in the third stage of the gearbox.

For both a summer month (left column) and a winter month (right column), the following quantities are shown:

- the measured load signals (torque and rotational speed),
- the cumulative pitting damage for gear 1 and gear 2.

The damage calculations are carried out for three reliability levels: 50%, 90%, and 99%. The highest damage levels are obtained for the 99% reliability case. This is due to the larger life modification factor (Zz-factor), which accounts for statistical variability in fatigue strength. In practical terms, this means that when the calculated damage reaches 1 at 99% reliability, approximately only 1 out of 100 gears is expected to have failed due to pitting at that point in time. The spread between the different reliability levels illustrates the significant statistical uncertainty inherent to fatigue processes.

A key observation from the results is that the damage accumulation is dominated by periods of high torque and high rotational speed. This is a direct consequence of the exponential nature of the S–N curves: relatively short load peaks contribute disproportionately to the total damage. As a result, accurate representation of these peaks is essential for reliable lifetime prediction.

Figure 5: Comparison of measured load signals (torque and rotational speed) and the resulting cumulative pitting damage for the third-stage parallel helical gears over one month of operation, comparing summer (left) and winter (right) conditions.

The comparison between summer and winter data further highlights differences in operational loading conditions. Variations in wind conditions lead to different load distributions, which directly translate into differences in damage accumulation rates.

The most important conclusion from this analysis is the strong influence of the load sampling strategy. When the load signal is averaged over 10-minute intervals (state-of-the-art practice), short-term load peaks are smoothed out. As a result, the calculated damage is approximately 10% lower compared to calculations based on 1-second load data. Since fatigue damage is highly sensitive to peak loads, this averaging leads to a systematic underestimation of the actual damage, once again reflecting the exponential nature of the S–N curves.

3.2.6 Strain-based mesh load factor estimation

Definition of mesh load factor K_γ

According to ISO 6336-1 [1], the mesh load factor K_γ is defined as the ratio between the highest load carried by an individual planet and the average load shared by all planets in a planetary gear stage. Ideally, $K_\gamma = 1$, corresponding to perfectly equal load sharing; however, deviations arise due to manufacturing tolerances, assembly errors, misalignments, and elastic deformations.

Experimentally, the mesh load factor can be estimated from strain measurements by analysing the response of individual sensor locations. As illustrated in Figure 6, the strain signal of a single sensor shows distinct peaks corresponding to the passage of each planet gear. The peak-to-peak value of each signal, defined by the difference between the maximum and minimum strain during one revolution, is used as a measure of the load carried by that planet. The mesh load factor for planet i is then determined as: $K_{\gamma,i} = \frac{\Delta_i}{\Delta_{all}}$, where Δ_i is the peak-to-peak strain associated with planet i , and Δ_{all} is the average peak-to-peak strain over all planets, evaluated over a full shaft revolution.

Figure 6: Example of strain signal measured on the ring gear, showing distinct peaks corresponding to the passage of individual planets.

A distinction is made between instantaneous and average values of K_y . The instantaneous mesh load factor is computed from a single revolution and captures short-term load variations between planets. The average mesh load factor is obtained by averaging Δ_i over multiple revolutions, providing a representative value of the long-term load distribution.

Historical measurement campaign

Historic data from ZF coming from a back-to-back test rig were used to experimentally determine the mesh load factors of two planetary stages. Torque and rotational speed were measured on both sides of the gearbox. Additionally, strain and acceleration measurements were performed on the ring gears of two planetary stages.

For the first planetary stage, which consists of four planets, seven strain gauges were installed at angular positions from 0° to 90° and from 285° to 345° , both in increments of 15° . The second stage, containing three planets, was instrumented with strain gauges positioned from 0° to 105° in increments of 15° , as well as at 345° . The test conditions involved operation at a constant rotational speed with a stepwise increase in the applied torque across four distinct load levels.

Data Processing and Results

The raw strain measurements were processed according to the methodology described in [2]. The peak-to-peak strain values were used as a proxy for the transmitted force, enabling the estimation of the mesh load factor for each planet. The results are summarized in Figure 7, where both the spatial and instantaneous behaviour of the mesh load factor are presented.

The upper part of the figure corresponds to the first planetary stage, while the lower part represents the second stage. For each stage, the left-hand side shows the circumferential distribution of the average mesh load factor around the ring gear, whereas the right-hand side presents the distribution of the instantaneous mesh load factors for different torque levels.

The results indicate that the average mesh load factor is largely independent of the sensor position around the ring gear. Furthermore, the instantaneous load distribution becomes more uniform as the torque increases, together with the reduced spread in the values. This behaviour can be attributed to the decreasing influence of manufacturing tolerances and clearances under higher loading conditions.

This experimentally determined mesh load factor can be incorporated into the damage calculations as a function of the torque level, providing a more realistic representation of the load sharing between planets. In general, the measured mesh load factors are lower than the conservative values prescribed by IEC 61400-4 [10], which depend on the number of planets (see Table 1). These standard values are primarily intended for design purposes and therefore include built-in safety margins.

A comparison with the experimental data shows that the mesh load factor reaches a maximum of approximately 1.07 for the first stage (four planets) and 1.04 for the second stage (three planets), which is significantly lower than the corresponding standard values. Moreover, at the higher torque levels where the dominant contributions to fatigue damage occur the mesh load factor remains below 1.03. As a result, using the experimentally derived values leads to a more accurate estimation of the actual loading conditions and, consequently, of the accumulated damage.

Figure 7: Mesh load factor results for both planetary stages (top: first stage, bottom: second stage). Left: circumferential distribution around the ring gear. Right: instantaneous mesh load factor distributions for different torque levels.

Table 1: Mesh load factor K_γ values for planetary stages given by the standard IEC 61400-4 according to their number of planets.

Number of planets	3	4	5	6	7
Mesh load factor K_γ	1.10	1.25	1.35	1.44	1.47

3.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities

This section has presented the degradation modelling of the four most relevant gearbox failure mechanisms: pitting, tooth bending, tooth flank fracture, and micropitting, together with a comparison of different damage calculation approaches.

The comparison between calculation methods demonstrates that using a 10-minute averaged load signal results in an underestimation of the accumulated fatigue damage by approximately 10%. Although this deviation is smaller than the statistical variability typically associated with fatigue processes, it remains advisable to use 1-second torque measurements, when available.

Furthermore, the mesh load factor can be estimated more accurately using strain gauge measurements on the ring gear. The experimentally derived values are generally lower than those prescribed by standard design methods, which are intentionally conservative to ensure safe design.

Finally, the developed degradation models will be validated in Deliverable D5.5 through comparison with observed failures in operational gearboxes. This validation will assess whether the predicted failure modes correspond to actual failures for pitting and tooth bending, and whether the safety factor approaches provide reliable indicators for tooth flank fracture and micropitting.

4 DEGRADATION MODEL OF THE GENERATOR

4.1 Introduction to the generator degradation model

The generator is a key component in a wind turbine, and it is crucial to have a design and operation regime that ensures reliability. Hot spot temperature in the winding is considered as one of the most important factors in lifetime consumption of electrical machines. This is because lifetime of the winding insulation strongly depends on the thermal ageing at the operating temperatures [1]. Operating temperature in different parts of the generator depends on the electromagnetic losses, and the cooling system of the generator. Generator model developed here to predict temperatures includes both, based on two-way coupling between electromagnetic and thermal domains. Electromagnetic losses in different parts of the generator are first calculated and then transferred to thermal models as heat sources. Temperature distribution is then calculated including the effects of the cooling system. Temperatures are then transferred back to the electromagnetic model to modify temperature-dependent electromagnetic properties as resistivity and magnet remanent flux density. This process is done both in steady state, and in transient calculations, at every time step.

Lifetime calculations for the windings usually use thermal ageing empirical formulas based on Arrhenius equation [11]. This equation relates the reaction rate of a chemical reaction to temperature:

$$k = Ae^{(-E/RT)}$$

Where k is the reaction-rate constant, A is frequency factor describing the frequency of collision between reacting molecules, E is the activation energy for the given reaction, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the temperature.

A widely used model for insulation lifetime calculations based on Arrhenius equation is Dakin model [1]:

$$L = Ae^{(-B/T)}$$

Where L is lifetime, A is insulation lifetime at 0K, B is a material constant (depends on the insulation class), and T is temperature in K (here hotspot temperature).

The lifetime strongly depends on the insulation class that is related to the material used in the windings. Standards such as IEC have defined different insulation classes for electrical insulation with defined maximum safe operating temperature.

Table 2: Insulation classes

Insulation Class	Maximum operating hot-spot temperature
H	180 °C
F	155 °C
B	130 °C
A	105 °C

The lifetime is considered to be limited to only 20000 hours if generator operates constantly at the maximum allowed temperature for a specific insulation class. If the operating temperature is lower than the “reference” value, lifetime will be extended according to the lifetime formulas mentioned above.

When designing a generator, the winding temperature and insulation needs to be taken into consideration. This is trade-off between cost and design as materials with higher temperature limits are more

expensive but require less external cooling. The current generator model is using a through ventilated cooling system with air being cooled by a heat exchanger.

It is important to emphasize that lifetime estimation here is only related to the thermal ageing of the windings, and does not include faults (such as bearing faults) and manufacturing issues that can cause failures. While faults can usually be detected and handled with proper monitoring and maintenance routines, end of insulation lifetime causes great risks to the operation and usually needs a costly and time-consuming re-winding or replacing the generator.

4.2 Degradation model of the generator

The degradation model of the generator is designed to evaluate how hot spot temperatures at the windings affect the lifetime of the insulation. The generator model is created using ANSYS Motor-CAD 2025R2 and is used to simulate electrothermal performance. The Arrhenius-Dakin model is directly implemented in ANSYS Motor-CAD.

The temperature distribution in the generator is assessed by performing a steady state electrothermal simulation in ANSYS Motor-CAD. The figures below shows the temperature distribution in axial and radial view. From these results, it is clear that the highest temperatures are at the end stator windings. Hence, for the lifetime calculation, the temperature at this location will be the key factor. The external cooling can be seen in the figure below, where the airflow is marked with blue arrows.

Figure 8: Generator temperature distribution - Axial view

Figure 9: Generator temperature distribution - Radial view

Figure 10: Temperature distribution in the windings - Axial view

Transient duty cycle simulations

To evaluate thermal performance and lifetime, a transient duty cycle with a varying current load is defined. The transient electrothermal performance is simulated for the specified cycle. To examine how these duty cycles affect the lifetime of the insulation the Arrhenius-Dakin model is used.

The load cycle used is shown in the figure below.

Figure 11: Transient duty cycle

Effect of insulation class

Three different insulation classes have been tested with the load cycle on the generator model.

The hotspot temperature at the end windings for the load cycle is plotted below. A maximum temperature reached is 146.3°C when the generator is running on full load.

Figure 12: Hotspot temperature for the duty-cycle

The graph below shows the lifetime usage of winding insulation for three different insulation classes. If class F is used barely any lifetime is consumed, while with class A the consumption is significant. Most of the lifetime is lost when running at full speed where the temperatures exceed 130°C.

Figure 13: Lifetime consumption comparing three insulation classes

Table below shows the hours of lifetime consumed over the course of the 8.3 hours duty-cycle.

Table 2: The lifetime consumed for different insulation classes

Class	Lifetime consumed [hours]
A	48.6
B	9.9
F	1.7

This shows that the thermal loading is too high for both insulation materials of class A and B, but suitable for class F. The generator here is designed with class F, which is common industry practice for this application.

Effect of cooling flow rate

Lifetime strongly depends on the hotspot temperature, which is greatly affected by the cooling system. In this section, two flow rates of the cooling system have been compared. In the previous section, the cooling flow rate was at 100%. Here a case with 90% flow rate has been added for comparison. The figure below shows the results.

Figure 14: Lifetime consumption comparing two cooling flow rates

As expected, lifetime is consumed at a higher rate when the flow rate is reduced as the temperature in the system is increased. This highlights the design trade-off between lifetime consumption and cooling system costs.

4.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities

A lifetime estimation model has been presented in the previous section. The model is used to estimate the thermal degradation of the winding insulation, which is the critical component with respect to lifetime estimation of the generator. The lifetime-estimation model can be used both in the design stage (selection of insulation class material/the cooling system) and in operation for real time life-time estimation that optimizes performance.

In previous work, the generator model has been used as a basis for a reduced order model (ROM) that is part of the digital twin of the wind turbine that is being developed. Further work includes creating a lifetime estimation ROM based on the model presented here to be part of the digital twin framework.

5 DEGRADATION MODEL OF THE MAIN BEARING

5.1 Introduction to the main bearing degradation model

The degradation model for the main bearing is based on the methodology described in ISO 16281 [12], which applies a sliced (lamina-based) approach to bearing life prediction. This method allows the load distribution across the bearing to be evaluated in a detailed manner, taking into account variations along the circumference.

Bearing life, in this context, is inherently statistical and typically expressed in terms of the L10 life, defined as the number of revolutions or operating hours that 90% of a population of identical bearings are expected to exceed under given operating conditions. Due to the natural variability in material, manufacturing, and operating conditions, individual bearing lifetimes can deviate significantly from this value, making precise prediction of the remaining useful life for a specific bearing challenging. Nevertheless, the model remains highly valuable, as it provides a physically grounded assessment of damage accumulation, highlights critical load regions, and indicates whether the bearing operates within or outside its intended design envelope. As such, it offers important insight into the remaining useful life at system level and supports both condition monitoring and design evaluation.

A wind turbine main bearing typically consists of two bearings: an upwind bearing and a downwind bearing. In the system considered here, the main shaft is supported by a Compact Aligning Roller Bearing (CARB), type C39/1500, on the upwind side, and a spherical roller bearing (SRB), type 240/1180 CAF/W33, on the downwind side. In this study, the focus is placed on the SRB, as it provides the most relevant data for detailed degradation analysis. A sectional view of the SRB is provided in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Sectional view of the spherical roller bearing used as the downwind main bearing.

To provide realistic input for the model, historical sensor roller data are used. These measurements are available for a period of 1.5 years and allow the load distribution within the bearing to be determined as a function of the angular position. The measurements show that the highest load zones occur around angular positions of approximately 110° and 250° , which are therefore expected to be the most critical regions for failure initiation.

Unlike indirect measurement approaches, this technology captures the actual internal response of the bearing, including the effects of structural flexibility, mounting conditions, and transient operating states. As such, it offers a high-fidelity representation of the circumferential load distribution that can be directly used for model calibration and validation. As will be show, the measurements show that the highest load zones occur around angular positions of approximately 110° and 250° , which are therefore expected to be the most critical regions for failure initiation.

Finally, the developed degradation models will be validated in Deliverable D5.5 by comparison with observed failures in operational systems. This validation will assess whether the predicted failure locations and mechanisms correspond to actual failures.

5.2 Degradation model of the main bearing

The degradation model combines measurement-based load inputs with standardized bearing life calculations. The following subsections describe the sensor roller measurements, load profile generation, and degradation calculation methodology.

5.2.1 Sensor rollers

Sensor rollers are used to directly measure the load distribution within the bearing. Each sensor roller is equipped with three strain gauges, positioned at the left, middle, and right sides of the roller. In addition, an accelerometer is integrated to determine the angular position and orientation of the roller within the bearing.

In total, six sensor rollers are installed in the main bearing system: two in the CARB bearing and four in the SRB. As this study focuses on the SRB, only the data obtained from the four sensor rollers located in the SRB are considered.

By combining the strain measurements with positional information, the load acting on the bearing can be reconstructed as a function of the angular position. This enables a detailed characterization of the load distribution along the bearing circumference.

Figure 16: Sensor rollers used for in-situ load measurement in the main bearing as develop by SKF. The left image shows multiple sensor rollers, while the right image presents a cutaway view of a sensor roller, illustrating the internal components including strain gauges and measurement electronics. [13]

5.2.2 Load profile

The sensor roller measurements are processed to construct a load profile as a function of the bearing angle, see Figure 17. This profile captures both the magnitude and the angular distribution of the loads acting on the bearing over time.

Figure 17: Load distribution in the main bearing as a function of angular position

Each sensor roller is equipped with three strain gauges, allowing the load to be resolved into three components across the roller width. These correspond to the load on the left, middle, and right contact zones of the bearing. When viewing the drivetrain from the rotor side towards the gearbox, load 1, 2 and 3 represent respectively the left, central, and right portions of the load distribution along the bearing width. The total load acting on the bearing at a given angular position is obtained by summing these three contributions.

For each of these load components, as well as for the total load, a characteristic angular load profile is obtained. These profiles exhibit a non-uniform distribution, with distinct load concentrations at specific angular positions. In particular, the highest loads are observed around angular positions of approximately 110° and 250°, which can be identified as the most critical zones for fatigue damage initiation.

From these load profiles, a statistical distribution of the loads is derived. The measured loads over the considered time period are assumed to be representative and periodic, allowing them to be extrapolated for long-term degradation calculations. This statistical distribution forms the primary input for the degradation model described in the next section.

5.2.3 Degradation calculation

The degradation of the bearing is calculated using ISO 16281 [12], which defines a modified bearing life equation based on a lamina-based approach (see Figure 18 for a schematic of the lamina concept).

Figure 18: Lamina model [12]

The life is expressed as [12]:

$$L_{nmr} = a_1 \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \left\{ \left[a_{ISO} \left(\frac{e_c C_{ua}}{P_{ks}}, \kappa \right) \right]^{-9/8} \left[\left(\frac{q_{kci}}{q_{kei}} \right)^{-9/2} + \left(\frac{q_{kce}}{q_{kee}} \right)^{-9/2} \right] \right\} \right)^{-8/9}$$

In this formulation, the measured loads are incorporated into q_{kei} and q_{kee} , which represent the dynamic equivalent loads (in newtons) acting on a bearing lamina at the inner and outer rings, respectively.

The remaining parameters in the equation are defined as follows [14]:

- a_1 : life modification factor for reliability
- a_{ISO} : life modification factor based on a system approach
- e_c : contamination factor
- C_{ua} : fatigue load limit (N)
- P_{ks} : dynamic equivalent load (N) of bearing lamina k
- κ : lubrication factor
- q_{kci} : basic dynamic load rating (N) for the inner ring
- q_{kce} : basic dynamic load rating (N) for the outer ring

To account for varying operating conditions over time, the Palmgren–Miner rule is applied to calculate accumulated fatigue damage. Based on momentary life values, an Updated Statistical Life (USL) can be determined using:

$$L_{10m} = \frac{1}{\frac{U_1}{L_{10m1}} + \frac{U_2}{L_{10m2}} + \frac{U_3}{L_{10m3}} + \dots}$$

where:

L_{10m} : overall rating life at 90% reliability (million revolutions)

$L_{10m1}, L_{10m2}, \dots$: rating lives under constant operating conditions (million revolutions)
 U_1, U_2, \dots : fractions of life cycle spent under each condition, with $U_1 + U_2 + \dots + U_n = 1$.

Using this approach, the damage accumulation is calculated by combining the contributions from different load levels derived from the measured load distribution. The loads recorded over the measurement period are assumed to repeat periodically, enabling long-term damage prediction.

Failure is expected when the accumulated damage reaches a value of 1. However, due to the inherent statistical nature of fatigue, there is significant variability in bearing lifetime. Therefore, life calculations can be performed for different reliability levels, such as L_{10}, L_{50} , and others, to better capture this statistical spread.

5.3 Conclusions and links to the other project activities

The presented degradation model combines detailed load measurements from sensor rollers with the ISO 16281 life calculation framework and Palmgren–Miner damage accumulation. This enables a realistic and physically grounded prediction of bearing lifetime and damage evolution.

The use of measured load distributions significantly improves the accuracy of the model compared to idealized assumptions. In addition, the inclusion of statistical life approaches allows the variability in bearing performance to be properly accounted for.

Finally, the developed degradation models will be validated in Deliverable D5.5 through comparison with observed failures in operational systems. This validation will assess whether the predicted failure locations and mechanisms correspond to actual field observations.

6 DEGRADATION MODEL OF THE PITCH AND YAW BEARING

6.1 Introduction to the pitch and yaw bearing degradation models

Wind turbine pitch and yaw bearings operate under highly variable loading conditions driven by aerodynamic forces, rotor dynamics, and control actions. These components are subjected to combinations of axial loads, radial loads, and overturning moments, resulting in complex rolling contact conditions at the interface between rolling elements and raceways. Under such conditions, and according to Laulagun historical data, the degradation is primarily governed by Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF), which is characterised by subsurface crack initiation driven by multiaxial stress states.

This common degradation mechanism provides the basis for treating pitch and yaw bearings within the same modelling framework. Although they perform different functions in the wind turbine, both are large slewing orientation bearings operating under low-speed, highly loaded and often oscillatory conditions. Their load histories and geometrical parameters differ, but the local damage process considered in this deliverable is governed by the same rolling contact conditions and subsurface stress mechanisms. For this reason, the methodology developed in this section is formulated generically and can be applied to both bearing types using the corresponding component-specific inputs.

Different RCF approaches can be found in literature. However, two fundamental challenges remain unresolved in the current state of the art.

- Lack of consensus on the governing fatigue parameter: RCF occurs under multiaxial, non-proportional stress states, where both normal and shear stresses evolve over time and space within the material. Numerous fatigue criteria have been proposed in the literature to describe crack initiation under such conditions, including critical plane approaches, shear-based criteria, and energy-based formulations. Despite this extensive work, there is no general agreement on which fatigue parameter is most appropriate for RCF applications, particularly for large-scale components such as wind turbine bearings.
- Fatigue damage evaluation under variable loading in real time: The second major challenge arises from the need to evaluate fatigue damage under variable amplitude loading conditions, as experienced in real wind turbine operation. The classical approach relies on: cycle counting methods (typically rainflow counting), S–N fatigue curves, and cumulative damage rules such as Miner’s rule. While this framework is well established and widely accepted, it presents a fundamental limitation: Fatigue damage is not evaluated continuously in time, but only when load cycles are identified and closed. As a consequence, the damage accumulation may appear delayed with respect to the applied load history, there is no direct mapping between the instantaneous stress state and the instantaneous damage rate, and then, the methodology is not naturally suited for real-time monitoring.

This limitation becomes critical when attempting to integrate fatigue models into operational frameworks, where continuous damage tracking is required.

Within this context, the present work addresses both challenges through two complementary developments:

- A methodology for the identification and evaluation of fatigue parameters in RCF, based on: the inverse characterization from RCF-specific experiments, and the introduction of modified testing conditions to discriminate between competing criteria. It should be noted that: the validation of fatigue parameters through dedicated experimental campaigns, and the final selection

of the governing fatigue criterion are addressed in T5.4 / D5.5, where testing procedures and specimen configurations are described in detail.

- A degradation model capable of evaluating fatigue damage under variable loading, including: a reference implementation based on rainflow counting with memory, ensuring consistency with classical fatigue theory, and the development of an incremental damage model, enabling continuous evaluation of fatigue damage and compatibility with real-time applications

6.2 Degradation model of the pitch and yaw bearing

6.2.1 Evaluation of Fatigue Parameters in Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF)

Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF) in bearing applications is governed by complex subsurface stress states that differ significantly from those typically encountered in standard fatigue testing. In particular, the stress field generated under rolling contact is multiaxial, non-proportional, and spatially heterogeneous, with strong gradients in the near-surface region. Under these conditions, fatigue damage initiation cannot be associated with a single stress component and therefore requires the definition of an appropriate fatigue parameter capable of capturing the governing damage mechanisms. Although numerous fatigue criteria have been proposed in the literature including shear-based, critical plane, and energy-based approaches a fundamental limitation is that standard fatigue tests (e.g., uniaxial or pure shear, or even combination) do not reproduce the actual subsurface stress conditions of RCF, making the characterization invalid, and the selection of a governing fatigue parameter uncertain.

The objective of this task is to establish a robust and physically consistent methodology for the evaluation and comparison of candidate fatigue parameters for RCF in wind turbine bearings. The aim is not only to ensure that the selected parameter can reproduce experimental observations under controlled conditions, but also that it retains predictive capability when applied to different stress states representative of real operating conditions. This requires moving beyond traditional calibration approaches and introducing a framework in which candidate parameters can be effectively discriminated.

The main steps of the approach are:

- Identification of candidate fatigue parameters from the literature, focusing on criteria with a clear physical interpretation for multiaxial fatigue and RCF conditions.
- Initial calibration of all parameters using experimental data obtained from RCF tests (task 5.5) on flat specimens, ensuring that the stress field is representative of rolling contact.
- Design of modified test configurations (e.g., geometric or loading variations) aimed at altering the subsurface stress field while preserving realistic RCF conditions.
- Predictive assessment of fatigue life under these modified conditions, enabling comparison of the sensitivity and predictive capability of each parameter.

This deliverable focuses on the definition of the methodology, the initial characterization, and the comparative predictive assessment of candidate fatigue parameters. The experimental validation of the proposed configurations, as well as the final selection of the governing fatigue criterion, are addressed in T5.4 / D5.5, where the testing procedures and specimen configurations are described in detail. It should also be noted that the degradation modelling framework developed in this work is independent of the specific fatigue parameter employed, allowing for a consistent evaluation of all candidates at this stage and facilitating the integration of the selected parameter in subsequent tasks.

Literature review and parameter selection

A set of fatigue parameters commonly used in multiaxial fatigue and Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF) has been reviewed and selected as candidates for evaluation. These parameters differ in their physical

interpretation, ranging from purely shear-driven mechanisms to combined normal–shear or energy-based approaches. The following list summarizes the most relevant criteria considered in this work, and an illustrative figure of the distribution of each implemented parameter.

Von Mises Equivalent Stress is defined by following equation:

$$\sigma_{VM} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2]}$$

$$\sigma_{VM} = \sqrt{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_z^2 - (\sigma_x\sigma_y + \sigma_y\sigma_z + \sigma_x\sigma_z) + 3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{xz}^2)}$$

An energy-based criterion widely used in yielding and fatigue. It represents the distortional energy in the material but does not distinguish between shear and normal contributions in terms of crack initiation mechanisms. Its applicability to RCF is debated [15].

Maximum Shear Stress (Tresca-type) is defined by following equation:

$$\tau_{max} = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2}$$

This parameter assumes that fatigue damage is governed by the maximum shear stress acting in the material. It is particularly relevant for subsurface RCF, where crack initiation is often associated with shear-driven mechanisms below the contact surface. It does not explicitly account for normal stresses or mean stress effects [16].

Orthogonal Shear Stress is defined by following equation:

$$\tau_{\perp} = \text{shear stress on planes orthogonal to rolling direction}$$

This parameter focuses on shear stresses acting on planes orthogonal to the rolling direction, which are considered critical for subsurface crack initiation in bearings. It is directly linked to classical bearing life theories and RCF-specific observations [17].

Dang Van Criterion is defined by following equation:

$$\sigma_{DV} = \max(\tau(t) + \alpha \cdot \sigma_h(t))$$

A mesoscopic fatigue criterion based on the combination of instantaneous shear stress and hydrostatic stress. It is designed to capture microstructural slip mechanisms and is particularly suited for high-cycle fatigue where damage accumulates at the grain level [18].

Shear Stress Intensity is defined by following equation:

$$\tau_{eff} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\gamma=0}^{\pi} \int_{\alpha=0}^{2\pi} \tau_{\gamma\alpha}^2 \sin \gamma \, d\alpha \, d\gamma}$$

An invariant measure of the shear stress state, combining multiple shear components into a single scalar quantity. It provides a global representation of shear intensity but does not explicitly consider directional effects or critical planes [19].

Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) Parameter is defined by following equation:

$$\sigma_{SWT} = \sigma_{n,max} \frac{\epsilon_{n,max}}{2}$$

A strain-based fatigue criterion that combines the maximum normal strain amplitude with the maximum normal stress on the critical plane. By incorporating the mean stress effect through the peak stress term, it is well-suited for tensile-dominated failure modes and is widely applied in low- and high-cycle fatigue assessment of metallic components [20].

McDiarmid Criterion is defined by following equation:

$$\sigma_{MCD} = \frac{\Delta\tau_{max}}{2} + \frac{R_e}{2R_m}\sigma_{n,max}$$

A stress-based multiaxial fatigue criterion that evaluates damage on the critical plane by combining the maximum shear stress amplitude with the maximum normal stress acting on that plane. It distinguishes between case A and case B crack systems through the corresponding fatigue strength, making it particularly suitable for high-cycle fatigue assessment under non-proportional loading and contact problems. [21]

For illustrative purposes, the image panel shown in Figure 19 is presented, where the stress distribution through the depth can be observed for each fatigue parameter introduced in this section. It can be observed slight differences in the stress field, locating the maximum values at different depths.

Figure 19: Illustrative example of all the parameters field stress distribution.

Table 3: Summary of all the parameters, indicating their sensitivity to different multiaxial criteria, as well as their applicability.

Parameter	Governing Mechanism	Sens. to Shear	Sens Normal	Mean Stress	Suitability
von Mises Stress	Distortional energy	Moderate	Moderate	No	Medium–Low
Maximum Shear Stress	Pure shear-driven	High	None	No	High
Orthogonal Shear Stress	Shear on critical planes	High	None	No	Very High
Dang Van	Microstructural shear + hydrostatic stress	High	Moderate (hydrostatic)	Yes (instantaneous)	High
Shear Stress Intensity	Global shear invariant	Moderate	None	No	Medium

Inverse characterization of fatigue parameters from RCF experimental

The inverse characterization of fatigue parameters in this work is based on Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF) tests rather than conventional fatigue testing methods (e.g., uniaxial or torsional tests). This choice is motivated by the fundamental differences between the stress states generated in standard tests and those occurring in bearing applications. As mentioned in the introduction of this section, under rolling contact conditions, the material experiences multiaxial, non-proportional stress states with strong subsurface gradients, where fatigue damage is primarily driven by shear mechanisms below the surface. These conditions are not reproduced in standard fatigue tests, which typically involve simplified and proportional loading states. As a result, fatigue parameters calibrated using conventional tests may not be physically representative for RCF. By using RCF-specific tests, the actual subsurface stress field responsible for crack initiation is directly reproduced, ensuring that the characterized fatigue parameters are consistent with the underlying damage mechanisms and suitable for bearing applications. The detailed description of the experimental setup, specimen manufacturing procedure, test rig, contact configuration and test execution will be provided in the delivery associated with T5.4 / D5.5. In the present deliverable, the experimental campaign is used as input for the fatigue characterization methodology.

The available experimental results consist of the number of cycles to failure (see Figure 20) obtained for different maximum contact pressure levels, see Figure 21.

Figure 20: Tested specimen after fail: left side shows plane specimen raceway, right side shows raceway damage spalling

Figure 21: Summary of tests performed on different sizes for inverse characterization of parameters

Each test condition is therefore defined by a pair:

$$p_0 - N_f$$

where p_0 is the maximum Hertzian contact pressure and N is the experimentally observed number of cycles to failure. For each pressure level, the corresponding subsurface stress field is computed using the contact model, and each candidate fatigue parameter is evaluated within the material domain. The maximum value of each fatigue parameter is then extracted and associated with the experimental fatigue life. In this way, the original experimental relation between contact pressure and life is transformed into an equivalent fatigue relation between each fatigue parameter and life:

$$p_0 \rightarrow P_{fat,max} \rightarrow N_f$$

where $P_{fat,max}$ denotes the maximum value of the selected fatigue parameter.

For each fatigue parameter, an S–N curve is obtained by fitting the experimental results in logarithmic space using a Basquin-type relationship:

$$P_{fat,max} = A \cdot N^b$$

or equivalently:

$$\log_{10}(N) = \alpha + \beta \log_{10}(P_{fat,max})$$

The scatter observed in the experimental results is represented by assuming a statistical distribution of fatigue life in logarithmic space. Based on this assumption, probability curves are derived for different probability levels, typically 5%, 50% and 95%. The 50% curve represents the median fatigue life, while the 5% and 95% curves represent lower and upper probability bounds of the fatigue life distribution.

This procedure is repeated independently for all candidate fatigue parameters, see Figure 22. As all parameters are calibrated using the same RCF experimental data, the resulting normalized S–N curves are expected to be equivalent in the initial characterization step, see Figure 23. Therefore, this stage does not directly identify the most suitable fatigue parameter but provides a consistent basis for comparing their predictive capability under modified stress states in subsequent analyses.

Figure 22: Inverse characterization of fatigue parameters from RCF experimental

Figure 23: Normalized curves obtained from same characterization

Design of modified test conditions to enhance differences between parameters

The inverse characterization procedure described in the previous section provides a consistent and physically grounded way to derive fatigue curves for all candidate parameters from RCF experimental data. However, an inherent limitation arises from this approach: when different fatigue parameters are calibrated using the same experimental dataset, they tend to produce equivalent normalized S–N curves.

This effect, referred to here as the normalization problem, is a direct consequence of the inverse fitting process. Since each fatigue parameter is independently mapped to the same set of experimental failure points, the calibration effectively compensates for differences in their physical formulation.

In order to overcome this limitation, it is necessary to introduce modified testing configurations capable of generating alternative subsurface stress states while preserving the essential characteristics of RCF. The objective of these configurations is not to redefine the fatigue model, but to amplify the intrinsic differences between competing fatigue parameters, enabling their comparative assessment.

Several strategies can be considered to achieve this objective:

- Modification of the stress state composition, for example by introducing additional loading components that alter the balance between shear and normal stresses.
- Variation of geometric conditions, such as introducing curvature in the raceway, which modifies the contact mechanics and the resulting stress gradients.

Two alternative test configurations were considered to improve the discrimination between candidate fatigue parameters and support the selection of the most suitable one for the analysed RCF failure mechanism. The objective was not only to generate a different subsurface stress state, but also to do so under conditions that remain comparable to the reference test. In this way, differences in predicted fatigue life can be attributed mainly to the response of each fatigue parameter, rather than to undesired scale effects or non-equivalent test conditions.

The first configuration is the interference test, shown in Figure 24(a). In this configuration, circumferential pretension is induced by introducing an interference fit at the inner diameter of the specimen during assembly. This approach is attractive because the original rolling contact conditions can be largely preserved while an additional stress component is introduced. The specimen is designed in two parts: a ring-shaped raceway and a slightly oversized inner insert. When assembled, the insert expands the raceway and induces circumferential stresses. However, the main limitation of this configuration is that the stress introduced by the interference is static and does not evolve as the rolling elements pass through the contact. As a result, it mainly modifies the mean stress state, while the cyclic stress range remains essentially unchanged. Since the objective is to discriminate fatigue parameters under cyclic RCF conditions, this configuration was discarded in favour of the conforming test.

The second configuration is the conforming test, shown in Figure 24(b). In this case, the subsurface stress field is modified through the geometry of the ball–raceway contact, by changing the degree of conformity between the rolling element and the raceway. This configuration directly affects the rolling contact stress distribution and therefore provides a more suitable basis for discriminating between fatigue parameters. To ensure that the conforming test remains comparable to the reference test, different raceway radii were evaluated. The aim was to identify a configuration that produces a subsurface stressed volume close to that of the reference test at the same maximum contact pressure. This is important because differences in stressed volume could introduce scale effects and mask the actual sensitivity of the fatigue parameters. Since each fatigue parameter defines a different stressed volume, the von Mises stress field was used as a common reference criterion for the volume-matching process, as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 26: Different specimens used for RCF parameter evaluation. Left-side image shows plane specimen for parameter characterization; right-side image shows conforming specimen for parameter selection

Table 4 compares the results obtained for the different conforming raceway configurations with the reference test. Among the analysed cases, the raceway radius of 10.5 mm provides the closest match in terms of stressed volume. Therefore, this configuration was selected as the preferred conforming test: it preserves an equivalent stressed volume with respect to the reference case, while generating a sufficiently different subsurface stress state to enhance the discrimination between candidate fatigue parameters. Figure 26 shows the plane specimen for parameter characterization, and the conforming specimen for parameter selection designed and manufactured according to this task.

Figure 24: Test configuration: left-side image show interference test and right-side image shows conforming test

Figure 25: Comparison between tests: VM distribution in reference test (a) and in conforming test (b).

Figure 26: Different specimens used for RCF parameter evaluation. Left-side image shows plane specimen for parameter characterization; right-side image shows conforming specimen for parameter selection

Table 4: Results for different conforming test configurations.

DATA		REF		CONF1		CONF2		CONF3	
Pressure		2894.69	MPa	2897.65	MPa	2897.11	MPa	2898.18	MPa
Øball		25.2	mm	14.1	mm	14.1	mm	14.1	mm
Rraceway		1000	mm	11	mm	10	mm	10.5	mm
Load		1700	N	1350	N	1600	N	1460	N
STRESSED VOLUME [mm3]									
VM		598		528	-12%	632	6%	577	-4%
MaxS		660		622	-6%	757	15%	677	3%
OrthS		378		529	40%	683	81%	598	58%
DV		767		713	-7%	873	14%	784	2%
SIH		584		516	-12%	622	7%	565	-3%
PARAMETER VALUES [MPa]									
VM	MPa	1794.88		1770.84	-1%	1761.07	-2%	1766.77	-2%
MaxS	MPa	897.48		938.59	5%	940.93	5%	940.34	5%
OrthS	MPa	617.06		682.88	11%	692.81	12%	688.12	12%
DV	MPa	656.18		691.97	5%	692.91	6%	692.61	6%
SIH	MPa	656.32		647.41	-1%	643.82	-2%	645.91	-2%

Predictive assessment under modified conditions for experimental validation of parameters

The relative differences reported in the previous table indicate that the conforming test may generate sufficiently distinct predictions between the candidate fatigue parameters. However, these differences must be interpreted in the context of the inherent scatter of fatigue phenomena. A difference between two predicted lives is only useful for parameter discrimination if it is large enough compared with the expected experimental variability. Otherwise, the results obtained from a future test campaign could overlap significantly, making it difficult to determine whether the observed differences are caused by the fatigue parameter itself or by the natural scatter of the fatigue process.

For this reason, a probabilistic assessment was carried out to evaluate whether the predicted differences between fatigue parameters are expected to be experimentally distinguishable. The S–N curves

used in this work were generated with ProFatigue, which provides fatigue curves associated with different target failure probabilities. The underlying probabilistic model is based on a modified Weibull distribution developed by UNIOVI. From the Weibull parameters provided by the software, probability density functions (PDFs) can be derived for the predicted fatigue lives of each candidate parameter.

These PDFs were used to assess the degree of overlap between the predicted fatigue-life distributions. A low overlap indicates that the relative differences between parameters are large compared with the expected fatigue scatter, and therefore that the proposed test configuration has good discriminating capability. Conversely, a high overlap indicates that the predicted differences may not be sufficient to draw a robust conclusion from experimental results.

Figure 27 show the predicted results for conforming test configuration and different parameters. The predicted distribution associated with the orthogonal shear parameter is clearly shifted towards lower fatigue lives and shows limited overlap with most of the other criteria. Therefore, this parameter would be expected to be relatively easy to confirm or discard experimentally. The maximum shear and Dang Van parameters form an intermediate group with similar predicted lives, meaning that they may be distinguishable from the lower- and higher-life groups, but are more difficult to discriminate from each other. In contrast, the reference, von Mises and shear stress intensity criteria show strongly overlapping distributions. This indicates that the proposed test configuration may not be sufficient to clearly distinguish between these parameters. However, this also suggests that, under the analysed stress conditions, these criteria provide similar fatigue-life predictions and may therefore be considered functionally equivalent for the purpose of the present degradation assessment.

Figure 27: Example of the Weibull curves obtained from reference tests.

6.3 Degradation modelling under variable loading for online predictions

The evaluation of fatigue damage in wind turbine pitch and yaw bearings is strongly influenced by the variable and stochastic nature of their operating loads. Under such conditions, the stress state evolves continuously over time, generating non-periodic stress histories at each point of the raceway. Classical fatigue assessment based on rainflow counting provides a robust and well-established approach, but damage is only updated when load cycles are identified and closed. This makes the damage evaluation discrete and potentially delayed with respect to the applied loading history.

To address this limitation, a hybrid modelling strategy is proposed. A rainflow-memory formulation is implemented as a reference approach, preserving consistency with classical fatigue assessment and accounting for open cycles across consecutive load blocks. In parallel, an incremental formulation is developed to provide continuous, time-resolved damage updates without requiring explicit cycle closure at each time step.

In this framework, the incremental model is not intended to replace the rainflow-based approach. Instead, it provides short-term damage tracking, while the rainflow-memory model runs in parallel as a longer-term reference. The comparison between both estimates over predefined time windows can be used to correct or recalibrate the incremental formulation, limiting long-term drift while maintaining compatibility with continuous monitoring and future digital twin applications.

Reference fatigue model based on rainflow counting

The reference degradation model adopted in this work follows a classical fatigue assessment framework, in which the complete sequence from external loads to accumulated damage is explicitly represented. The objective of this formulation is to provide a physically consistent baseline, fully aligned with established fatigue theory, against which alternative approaches can be compared.

The process begins with the definition of the external loading conditions acting on the bearing. These loads, derived from wind turbine operation, include axial forces, radial forces, and overturning moments. For each time step, these global loads are translated into the internal load distribution acting on the rolling elements through a dedicated mechanical model of the component, developed in task 4.2 and presented in previous deliverables:

$$\{F_x, F_y, F_z, M_x, M_y\} \rightarrow \{N_i(t), M_i(t)\}$$

where $N_i(t)$ and $M_i(t)$ represent the normal load and moment acting on each rolling element i at time t .

Once the load distribution is obtained, the local contact conditions are used to compute the corresponding subsurface stress field. This is achieved through a reduced-order model of the rolling contact problem, which provides the stress tensor as a function of the local contact load, developed in task 4.2 and presented in previous deliverables:

$$\sigma(x, y, z, t) = f(N_i(t), M_i(t))$$

This relation captures the nonlinear contact mechanics and provides the full three-dimensional stress field within the material domain for each time step.

From the stress tensor, the selected fatigue parameter is evaluated at every point in the domain. In general, this can be expressed as:

$$P_{fat}(t) = g(\sigma(t))$$

where $g(\cdot)$ represents the chosen fatigue criterion (e.g., maximum shear stress, Findley, Dang Van, etc.). By repeating this operation over the full load history, a time series of the fatigue parameter is obtained for each node:

$$\{P_{fat}(t_1), P_{fat}(t_2), \dots, P_{fat}(t_n)\}$$

This time history constitutes the input for the fatigue damage evaluation.

The fatigue damage calculation is performed using a rainflow counting algorithm applied to the time history of the fatigue parameter at each node. To ensure consistency when processing long signals, a rainflow implementation with memory is used, allowing the analysis to be carried out in blocks while preserving continuity across block boundaries. The algorithm decomposes the signal into a set of load cycles, each characterized by a range ΔP_i and a mean value \bar{P}_i .

For each identified cycle, a mean stress correction is applied using a Goodman-type formulation:

$$\Delta P_i^* = \frac{\Delta P_i}{1 - \frac{\bar{P}_i}{P_u}}$$

where P_u represents the material strength limit expressed in terms of the selected fatigue parameter.

The corrected cycle amplitude is then used to determine the number of cycles to failure through a Basquin-type S–N relationship:

$$P_{fat} = A \cdot N^b \Leftrightarrow N_i = \left(\frac{\Delta P_i^* / 2}{A} \right)^{1/b}$$

Finally, the damage contribution of each cycle is computed using Miner’s linear damage rule:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i}$$

where n_i represents the number of occurrences of each cycle. The total accumulated damage is obtained by summing the contribution of all cycles identified in the fatigue parameter history.

This procedure results in a spatial distribution of accumulated fatigue damage within the raceway, fully consistent with classical fatigue theory. It captures the effects of variable amplitude loading, mean stress influence, and the multiaxial nature of the stress field through the choice of fatigue parameter.

However, due to its reliance on cycle identification, the rainflow-based formulation does not provide a continuous representation of damage evolution in time, see Figure 28. Damage is only updated when cycles are closed, which introduces a delay between the applied loading and the computed damage. This limitation becomes particularly relevant in the context of real-time monitoring and motivates the development of the incremental formulation described in the following section.

Figure 28: Stress cycles and fatigue accumulation history through rainflow reference model on an illustrative node of bearing raceway.

Incremental fatigue model for continuous damage evaluation

In order to overcome the limitations associated with cycle-based fatigue evaluation, an incremental degradation model has been developed. The objective of this formulation is to enable a continuous estimation of fatigue damage directly from the time history of the fatigue parameter, avoiding the need for explicit cycle identification while preserving consistency with the reference rainflow-based approach.

The starting point of the incremental formulation is the same as in the reference model. The external loads are translated into rolling element forces, the subsurface stress field is computed, and the fatigue parameter is evaluated at each point in the domain. However, instead of storing the full history and applying a rainflow algorithm, the incremental model processes the fatigue parameter locally in time, considering only consecutive time steps.

The variation between two consecutive time steps is interpreted as an equivalent load event:

$$\Delta P_i = | P_{fat}(t_i) - P_{fat}(t_{i-1}) |$$

and the associated mean value is defined as:

$$\bar{P}_i = \frac{P_{fat}(t_i) + P_{fat}(t_{i-1})}{2}$$

This variation is assumed to represent an equivalent half-cycle, which allows the use of the same fatigue formulation as in the rainflow-based approach. A mean stress correction is applied using the same Goodman-type relationship:

$$\Delta P_i^* = \frac{\Delta P_i}{1 - \frac{\bar{P}_i}{P_u}}$$

The number of cycles to failure associated with this equivalent event is then obtained from the S–N relationship:

$$N_i = \left(\frac{\Delta P_i^* / 2}{A} \right)^{1/b}$$

and the corresponding damage increment is computed as:

$$\Delta D_i = C_{step} \cdot \frac{0.5}{N_i}$$

where the factor 0.5 reflects the half-cycle assumption and C_{step} is a global scaling parameter introduced to compensate for the simplifications inherent to the incremental representation.

The total accumulated damage is obtained by summing the contributions over all time steps:

$$D = \sum_i \Delta D_i$$

This formulation provides a fully continuous damage evolution, where each change in the fatigue parameter contributes directly to the accumulated damage. As a result, the model establishes a direct link between the instantaneous stress state and the instantaneous damage rate, making it suitable for time-resolved analysis and real-time applications.

The incremental formulation introduces a simplification with respect to the true cycle structure of the load history. In particular, complex load sequences that would be interpreted as closed cycles in the rainflow algorithm are approximated as a series of independent half-cycles. As a consequence, the raw incremental model does not inherently reproduce the same fatigue damage as the reference rainflow-based solution and requires calibration.

To ensure consistency between both approaches, a scaling factor C_{step} is introduced. In contrast to a purely global calibration, the approach adopted in this work allows for a node-dependent calibration, such that the scaling factor may vary spatially across the domain:

$$C_{step} = C_{step}(x, y, z)$$

This enables the incremental formulation to account for local differences in stress history characteristics, including amplitude variability, non-proportionality effects, and cycle interaction, which are not explicitly captured by the simplified incremental representation.

The calibration is performed by directly comparing the damage predicted by the incremental model with that obtained from the reference rainflow-based model over a representative set of load histories. For each node in the domain, the scaling factor is computed as:

$$C_{step}(x, y, z) = \frac{D_{rainflow}(x, y, z)}{D_{incremental}(x, y, z)}$$

where $D_{rainflow}$ corresponds to the accumulated damage obtained using the cycle-based formulation, and $D_{incremental}$ is the damage predicted by the incremental model using an initial unit scaling factor.

It should be noted that this calibration is not performed on a single load case, but on time histories representative of the full operational envelope of the wind turbine. In practice, this involves long-duration simulations including different wind speeds, turbulence intensities, and operating scenarios. The reference rainflow-based damage is computed over these life-representative time series, and the incremental model is calibrated accordingly at each node. This ensures that the resulting $C_{step}(x, y, z)$ field captures the statistical characteristics of the loading environment and remains valid across different operating conditions.

Once calibrated, the incremental model is applied using the obtained spatial distribution of C_{step} . The damage increment at each time step becomes:

$$\Delta D_i(x, y, z) = C_{step}(x, y, z) \cdot \frac{0.5}{N_i}$$

where N_i is computed from the corrected fatigue parameter variation, as described previously.

This localized calibration significantly improves the agreement between the incremental and rainflow-based models, not only in terms of maximum damage values but also in the spatial distribution of damage across the raceway. It allows the incremental formulation to retain its computational efficiency and continuous nature, while closely reproducing the physically grounded reference solution. Figure 29 shows the stress cycles and compares the fatigue damage accumulation obtained with the rainflow-memory reference model and the incremental formulation. The incremental model provides a continuous update of the damage history, while the rainflow-based reference updates damage only when cycles are identified and closed.

Figure 29: Stress cycles and comparative fatigue accumulation history through rainflow reference model and the incremental.

Numerical benchmarking against rainflow reference

The incremental damage formulation was numerically benchmarked against the rainflow-memory approach, which was used as the reference solution. The objective of this benchmarking exercise was to assess the capability of the incremental model, calibrated through a correction factor C_{step} , to reproduce both the magnitude and the spatial distribution of fatigue damage.

Two calibration strategies were considered: (i) a global calibration based on a single scalar C_{step} , and (ii) a node-wise calibration in which an individual C_{step} value is assigned to each node of the stress field. The calibration was performed using increasing lengths of the load time series, from $n_{\text{cal}} = 500$ to 12000 steps, and evaluated under two scenarios: same-series, where calibration and validation are performed on the same signal, and cross-series, where calibration and validation are performed on different signals. Spatial error metrics were computed only for relevant nodes, defined as $D_{\text{rf}} \geq 0.01 \cdot \max(D_{\text{rf}})$.

Table 5 and

Table 6 summarize the validation results for the same-series and cross-series cases, respectively, while Figure 30, Figure 31, and Figure 32 illustrate the evolution of the main error metrics with calibration length.

In the same-series case, the global calibration can reproduce the maximum damage when the full signal is used for calibration. However, its spatial accuracy remains limited, with mean errors consistently around 59%. This indicates that a single scaling factor is not sufficient to reproduce the spatial redistribution of fatigue damage. In contrast, the node-wise calibration shows a clear reduction of the spatial error metrics as the calibration length increases. With full calibration, the model reproduces the rainflow-memory reference with very low mean and P95 errors, demonstrating that the node-wise formulation can capture the spatial variability of damage when enough representative calibration data are available

Table 5: summarizes the results obtained when calibration and validation are performed on the same time series

Mode	n_cal	maxD error	Critical node error	Mean error	P95 error
Global	500	-6.6%	-7.9%	58.4%	93.0%
Global	2000	-12.3%	-13.6%	58.1%	92.8%
Global	8000	+6.4%	+4.9%	59.8%	97.5%
Global	12000	0.0%	-1.4%	58.9%	93.6%
Node	500	+178.1%	-17.8%	59.8%	208.6%
Node	2000	+124.8%	+11.3%	27.3%	81.7%
Node	8000	+34.2%	+21.5%	16.1%	48.3%
Node	12000	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	11.4%

Table 6: summarizes the results obtained when calibration and validation are performed on cross-series.

Mode	n_cal	maxD error	Critical node error	Mean error	P95 error
Global	500	-23.4%	-24.3%	61.3%	93.9%

Global	2000	-28.0%	-29.0%	61.5%	94.0%
Global	4000	+6.8%	+5.4%	63.9%	110.3%
Global	12000	-17.9%	-19.0%	61.4%	93.8%
Node	500	+203.3%	-40.4%	56.2%	172.6%
Node	2000	+182.7%	-21.3%	29.6%	68.9%
Node	8000	+56.2%	+8.7%	20.0%	48.0%
Node	12000	+3.5%	-17.8%	21.6%	47.2%

In the cross-series case, the global calibration again shows limited improvement with increasing calibration length, with mean errors remaining around 61–64%. This confirms that a single global correction factor has poor generalisation capability under changing load histories. The node-wise calibration performs significantly better and shows a clear convergence trend as n_{cal} increases. For the longest calibration length, the model achieves a maximum damage error of approximately 3.5%, a mean spatial error of approximately 21.6%, and a P95 error of approximately 47%. Although the residual error does not vanish as in the same-series case, the improvement over the global calibration is substantial.

The analysis of the maximum damage error shows higher variability, reflecting the sensitivity of this metric to local effects. However, the P95 error, which is representative of the most damaged regions, confirms that the node-wise formulation improves the estimation of damage in critical areas. In addition, the spatial location of the most damaged region is generally well captured, with the incremental model identifying critical zones close to those obtained with the rainflow-memory reference.

Figure 30: Convergence of mean spatial damage error with increasing calibration length for global and node-wise calibration strategies.

Figure 31: Convergence of maximum damage error with calibration length for global and node-wise calibration strategies.

Figure 32: Convergence of P95 spatial damage error with calibration length for global and node-wise calibration strategies.

Overall, these results show that the global calibration approach is inherently limited. It does not benefit significantly from longer calibration signals and fails to capture the spatial variability of fatigue damage. The node-wise calibration provides a much more accurate representation of the damage field, but the cross-series results also show that a fixed calibration may still lead to residual errors when the loading conditions change.

Therefore, the incremental model should not be interpreted as a standalone replacement for the rainflow-memory approach. Instead, the results support the use of a hybrid damage-tracking strategy. In this strategy, the incremental formulation provides short-term, time-resolved damage updates, while the rainflow-memory model runs in parallel as a longer-term reference. The comparison between both estimates over predefined time windows can be used to update the C_{step} field over time and to periodically correct the accumulated damage value. This would reduce long-term drift while preserving the continuous update capability required for future digital twin applications.

The node-wise calibration shows markedly different behavior. For short calibration lengths, the model exhibits instability and strong overestimation of damage. However, as the calibration length increases.

6.4 Conclusions and links to the other project activities

This section has presented the degradation modelling framework developed for pitch and yaw bearings, with a specific focus on Rolling Contact Fatigue (RCF) under variable loading conditions. The work addresses two complementary aspects: the evaluation of candidate fatigue parameters for RCF assessment and the definition of a damage accumulation strategy suitable for future continuous damage tracking.

Regarding fatigue-parameter evaluation, several multiaxial fatigue criteria were reviewed and implemented. The initial inverse characterisation based on RCF-specific tests allows equivalent S–N curves to be derived for each candidate parameter. However, this calibration alone is not sufficient to identify the most suitable criterion, since different parameters can reproduce the same reference tests after normalisation. Therefore, modified test configurations were analysed to generate alternative subsurface stress states and improve discrimination between competing criteria. Among the configurations considered, the conforming test was identified as the most suitable candidate for future experimental validation.

Regarding damage accumulation under variable loading, two complementary formulations were developed. The rainflow-memory model provides a reference solution consistent with classical fatigue assessment and accounts for open cycles across consecutive load blocks. In parallel, an incremental damage formulation was proposed to provide time-resolved damage updates without requiring explicit cycle closure at each time step. The incremental model was numerically benchmarked against the rainflow-memory reference using global and node-wise calibration strategies. The results show that a single global correction factor is not sufficient to reproduce the spatial distribution of fatigue damage. Node-wise calibration provides a more accurate representation of the damage field, although residual errors remain when the loading conditions differ from those used for calibration. This indicates that the incremental formulation should not be considered as a standalone replacement for the rainflow-memory approach, but rather as part of a hybrid damage-tracking strategy.

In this hybrid strategy, the incremental formulation provides short-term continuous damage updates, while the rainflow-memory model runs in parallel as a longer-term reference. The comparison between both estimates over predefined time windows can be used to update the C_{step} field over time and to periodically correct the accumulated damage value. This approach helps limit long-term drift while preserving the continuous update capability required for future digital twin applications.

Overall, the proposed framework provides a basis for both offline fatigue assessment and future hybrid damage tracking of pitch and yaw bearings. The link with Task 4.2 is direct, since the models use local contact loads, contact pressures and subsurface stress fields obtained from high- and mid-fidelity component models. The link with Task 4.4 is also central, as the rainflow-memory reference model, the incremental formulation, the calibrated C_{step} fields and the resulting damage indicators provide the basis for reduced or hybrid models suitable for integration into the ICONIC digital twin. Further work will focus on experimental validation of the fatigue-parameter selection methodology and on the assessment of the hybrid degradation strategy under representative operational load histories.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has presented the degradation modelling approaches developed in Task 4.3 for the critical wind turbine components considered within the ICONIC project. The work provides a methodological basis for translating local component responses and measurement-based inputs into damage indicators, lifetime consumption metrics and degradation descriptors. These models are intended to support subsequent reduction, integration and validation activities within the ICONIC digital twin framework, rather than acting as standalone final RUL prediction tools.

For the gearbox, ISO 6336-based degradation approaches were applied to the selected gear failure mechanisms considered in this deliverable: pitting, tooth bending, tooth flank fracture and micropitting. The comparison between 10-minute averaged torque signals and 1-second torque data showed that load time resolution can influence cumulative fatigue damage, with the averaged signal leading to an underestimation of accumulated pitting damage of approximately 10% in the analysed case. In addition, strain-based estimation of the planetary mesh load factor provided a more representative description of load sharing under the tested conditions, supporting more realistic gearbox damage indicators.

For the generator, the degradation model focused on thermal ageing of the stator winding insulation. Electrothermal simulations were used to evaluate winding hot-spot temperatures under transient duty-cycle operation, and the Arrhenius-Dakin formulation was applied to estimate insulation lifetime consumption. The results highlight the influence of insulation class and cooling flow rate on thermal degradation, providing a basis for future reduced-order thermal degradation indicators.

For the main bearing, the degradation approach combined sensor roller measurements with the ISO 16281 bearing life calculation framework and Palmgren-Miner damage accumulation. The use of measured load distributions enabled the identification of non-uniform circumferential loading in the downwind spherical roller bearing, with the most loaded zones located around 110° and 250°. This provides a physically based framework for estimating bearing lifetime indicators under measured operating conditions, pending further comparison with operational observations.

For the pitch and yaw bearings, the work addressed Rolling Contact Fatigue under multiaxial subsurface stress states and variable loading. A methodology was defined to compare candidate fatigue parameters using RCF-specific tests and modified test configurations designed to improve discrimination between criteria. In addition, damage accumulation under variable loading was addressed through a hybrid strategy combining a rainflow-memory reference model and an incremental damage formulation. In this framework, the incremental model provides short-term continuous damage updates, while the rainflow-memory model runs in parallel as a longer-term reference for periodically updating the C_{step} field and correcting accumulated damage drift.

Overall, D4.3 establishes the degradation modelling basis required for future component-level lifetime assessment within the ICONIC turbine-level digital twin framework. The next steps will focus on reducing or reformulating these models for digital twin integration in Task 4.4 and assessing their applicability through validation activities in WP5 using dedicated and/or historical operational and test-rig data. These activities will be necessary before the degradation indicators can be reliably used to support predictive maintenance, lifetime-aware control and LCOE-oriented decision-making.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO 6336-1:2019 Calculation of load capacity of spur and helical gears – Part 1: Basic principles, introduction and general influence factors,» International Organization for Standardization, 2019.
- [2] U. Gutierrez-Santiago, J. Keller, A. Fernández-Sisón, H. Polinder y J.-W. Van Wingerden, «Instantaneous mesh load factor (K_γ) measurements in a wind turbine gearbox using fiber-optic strain sensors,» *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2767, n° 4, p. 042022, 2024.
- [3] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO 6336-2:2019 Calculation of load capacity of spur and helical gears – Part 2: Calculation of surface durability (pitting),» International Organization for Standardization, 2019.
- [4] X. Liang y H. Zhang, , «The influence of tooth pitting on the mesh stiffness of a pair of external spur gears,» *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 2016, 2016.
- [5] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO 6336-3:2019 Calculation of load capacity of spur and helical gears – Part 3: Calculation of tooth bending strength,» International Organization for Standardization, 2019.
- [6] I. Boiadjev, J. Witzig, T. Tobie y K. Stahl, «Tooth flank fracture – Basic principles and calculation model for a sub-surface-initiated fatigue failure mode of case-hardened gears,» *Gear technology*, 2015.
- [7] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO/TS 6336-4:2019 Calculation of load capacity of spur and helical gears – Part 4: Calculation of tooth flank fracture load capacity,» International Organization for Standardization, 2019.
- [8] S. Rommel, R. Carranza Fernandez y T. Tobie, «Tooth flank fracture in a wind turbine gearbox—A failure analysis,» *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, vol. 2025, n° 89, p. 36, 2025.
- [9] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO/TR 6336-31:2018 Calculation of load capacity of spur and helical gears – Part 31: Example calculations for micropitting,» International Organization for Standardization, 2018.
- [10] L. Winkelmann, O. El-Saeed y M. Bell, «The effect of superfinishing on gear micropitting, Part II,» de *AGMA 08FTM10*, 2008.
- [11] International Electrotechnical Commission, «IEC 61400-4:2012 Wind turbines – Part 4: Design requirements for wind turbine gearboxes,» International Electrotechnical Commission, 2012.
- [12] Theofanous, A.; Ullah, I.; Galea, M.; Giangrande, P.; Madonna, V.; Ji, Y.; Licari, J.; Apap, M. Modelling of Insulation Thermal Ageing: Historical Evolution from Fundamental Chemistry Towards Becoming an Electrical Machine Design Tool. *Energies* 2025,.
- [13] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO/TS 16281: Rolling bearings – Methods for calculating the modified reference rating life for universally loaded bearings,» International Organization for Standardization, 2008.
- [14] Bearing News, «On a roll: Raising standards for collecting bearing data,» *Bearing News*, 28 June 2021. [En línea]. Available: <https://www.bearing-news.com/on-a-roll-raising-standards-for-collecting-bearing-data/>. [Último acceso: 13 May 2026].

- [15] International Organization for Standardization, «ISO 281: Rolling bearings – Dynamic load ratings and rating life,» International Organization for Standardization, 2007.
- [16] R. von Mises, “Mechanik der festen Körper im plastisch-deformablen Zustand,» Nachr. Ges. Wiss. Göttingen, Math.-Phys. Kl., vol. 1913, pp. 582–592, 1913.
- [17] H. Tresca, “Mémoire sur l’écoulement des corps solides soumis à de fortes pressions,» Mémoires présentés par divers savants à l’Académie des Sciences, vol. 18, pp. 733–799, 1868.
- [18] E. Ioannides and T. A. Harris, “A new fatigue life model for rolling bearings,» Journal of Tribology, vol. 107, no. 3, pp. 367–378, 1985.
- [19] K. Dang Van, G. Cailletaud, J. F. Flavenot, A. Le Douaron, and H. P. Lieurade, “Criterion for high-cycle fatigue failure under multiaxial loading,» in Biaxial and Multiaxial Fatigue, M. W. Brown and K. J. Miller, Eds. London, U.K.: Mechanical Engineering.
- [20] V. Papadopoulos, P. Davoli, C. Gorla, M. Filippini, and A. Bernasconi, “A comparative study of multiaxial high-cycle fatigue criteria for metals,» International Journal of Fatigue, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 219–235, 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0142-1123(96)00064-3.
- [21] K. N. Smith, P. Watson, and T. H. Topper, “A stress-strain function for the fatigue of metals,» Journal of Materials, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 767–778, 1970.
- [22] D. L. McDiarmid, “A general criterion for high cycle multiaxial fatigue failure,» Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 429–453, 1991.